

Transverse Sound I: Sub-Elastic Wave Theory

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Dedicated to my grandson Akaalbir, whose curiosity and sense of wonder I share

Abstract

It is a common belief in acoustics that transverse sound waves cannot be transmitted through fluids. In this first part of the two-part paper, both longitudinal and transverse sound waves are predicted to propagate through gases and liquids. The primary motivation for the present paper originated from the intention to explore the mechanics of gases and liquids as distinct sub-elastic states of matter. The sub-elastic materials are incapable of mobilising elastic resistance to full Cauchy stress tensor. First, the Sub-Elasticity Theory as a theory of sub-elastic mechanical systems or equivalently homogeneous mechanical systems is presented. Then, new distinct sub-elasticity theories of inviscid gases and liquids based on new versions of their equations of state, constitutive equations, equations of motion, and wave equations are presented. Here, Euler's dynamical equations of motion, the continuity equation, Laplace formula for speed of sound, and Poisson's wave theory of sound are not invoked. Using the new sub-elastic wave theory of sound, following expressions respectively for the speed of sub-elastic longitudinal and transverse sound waves are derived: $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma p}{\rho}}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$ for gases and $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{K}{\rho} \left(\frac{3-p/K}{3+p/K} \right)}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{-\frac{p}{2\rho} \left(\frac{3}{3+p/K} \right)}$ for elastic liquids. The expressions for speed of longitudinal waves through gases and liquids are identical or compatible with well-established formulae. The main contribution of the paper to acoustics is the prediction that both gases and liquids can support the propagation of transverse sound waves. Here, the sound waves as perturbations in the velocity field are termed as sub-elastic waves to distinguish them from elastic and pressure waves. In the accompanying second part of the paper (Benipal 2026), the theoretical and philosophical significance of the proposed theory are critically examined.

Keywords: Sub-elasticity, inviscid gas and liquid mechanics, constitutive equations, equations of motion, wave equations, acoustics, transverse waves.

1. Introduction

Ancient Indian concept of Akasha as acoustic aether (Prasad 2008) is reminiscent of later equally untenable concepts of gravitational and luminiferous aether. However, it became gradually clear that the material fields satisfy both the necessary and sufficient conditions for sound propagation and the vibrating bodies play the role of both source and sensor of sound waves. The theory of sound grew out of the curiosity during the early modern period about the mysterious phenomenon of echo apparently without an identified source. Later, echo was correctly understood to be reflected sound (van der Meisen 2020). Mersenne (1630) and Gassendi (1635) are credited with early measurements of speed of arial sound. Using the analogy with pendulous motion, the first expression $c = \sqrt{p/\rho}$ for the speed of sound waves through a gaseous medium was proposed by Newton (1687). However, this formula underestimated the observed speed of sound. It was Laplace (1816) who proposed a general isentropic formula for speed of sound in quiescent fluids $c = \sqrt{dp/d\rho}$ based on thermodynamic considerations. Assuming sound propagation to be an adiabatic process, Laplace proposed the adiabatic equation of state as $pV^\gamma = C$ or $p = D\rho^\gamma$. It yielded the corrected version $c = \sqrt{\gamma p/\rho}$ of Newton's formula for speed of aerial sound (Tokaty 1971). Earlier attempts by Euler and Lagrange to derive correct formulae proved unsuccessful. Krout and Sohrab have evaluated Newton's and Laplace's formulae in the light of kinetic theory of gases (Krout and Sohrab 2016).

According to Wirgin, using the above Laplace general formula, Colladon and Sturm (1837) obtained the expression for speed of sound through liquids as $c = \sqrt{K/\rho}$. Here, $K = p/\varepsilon_v$ represents their bulk modulus of elasticity and ε_v denotes small volumetric elastic strain (Wirgin, 2017).

However, these expressions for speed of sound do not capture the essentially wave nature of sound. The first linear wave theory of arial sound was proposed by Poisson (1820) in terms of scalar velocity potential ϕ . Hyperbolic wave equation $\nabla^2\phi = \frac{1}{c^2}\frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial t^2}$ where $c = \sqrt{dp/d\rho}$ was derived from linearized versions of the Laplace adiabatic equation of state relating pressure and density, the continuity equation, and the Euler's equation of motion. Poisson's wave theory is incorporated in Rayleigh's authoritative treatise entitled *The Theory of Sound* (Rayleigh 1877/1945). Later, hyperbolic wave equations of the form $\nabla^2 Z = \frac{1}{c^2}\frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial t^2}$ have been formulated variously in terms of velocity potential by Lamb (Lamb 1910), current placements by Rayleigh (Rayleigh 1877/1945) and Feynman (Feynman 1963a), pressure and density by Truesdell and Rajagopal (Truesdell and Rajagopal 2000) as well as by Herrin (Herrin 2012), and density by Jog (Jog 2002).

These wave equations are derived assuming sound as a small-amplitude perturbation in uniform pressure field for fluids at rest. Following Poisson, acoustic pressure and condensation are taken to represent small perturbations in pressure and density fields respectively. Using slightly different approaches, these derivations by other researchers obtain the same Laplace's formula for speed of irrotational arial sound wave. However, these stand-alone derivations are presented without any sense of historical priority and comparative evaluation. Thus, it seems that the required formulae were formulated by Laplace as well as Colladon and Sturm to

somehow predict the observed speed of sound respectively through gases and liquids while wave theories were formulated by Poisson (1820) and others to somehow derive Laplace general formula.

Euler's dynamical equations of motion (1755) of inviscid fluids are stated as $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + b_i = \rho \frac{Dv_i}{Dt}$

where the term $\frac{Dv_i}{Dt} = \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} + v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3}$ represents the material time derivative.

Also, based upon earlier work by James Bernoulli, Euler proposed the continuity equation as $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho v) = 0$ satisfying the principle of conservation of mass during flow of compressible fluids (Jog 2002; Darrigol 2005). Euler's theory of inviscid fluids has been used as the basis for constructing wave theories of sound and theories of viscous fluids. However, the foundations of Euler's theory itself have been criticised by later researchers.

Using the material time derivative of density field $\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + v \cdot (\nabla \rho)$, the above continuity equation is stated alternatively as $\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho(\nabla \cdot v)$. The commonly used incompressibility condition requires that $\nabla \cdot v = 0$ and so $\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = 0$. However, as per the definition of material derivative, this incompressibility condition holds only for steady flow ($\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = 0$) and uniform density field ($\nabla \rho = 0$). From these arguments put forward by Jog (Jog 2002), it seems that the fluid incompressibility condition needs a more general and consistent definition.

Further, stated in terms of pressure p and linear momentum density ρv , the continuity equation $\nabla \cdot (\rho v) = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{L} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t}$ for isothermal gases obeying Boyle's law $p = L\rho$ appears to the present author to be a mirror image of Euler law of motion $\nabla \cdot (pI) = \rho \frac{Dv_i}{Dt}$. Obviously, there is a need for more clarity on this matter.

The legendary mathematician and fluid dynamicist John von Neumann was critical of the 'unrealistic' concept of inviscid fluids and ridiculed those investigating its behavior as studying the non-existent "dry water", a term adopted by Feynman himself (Feynman 1963b). However, this Dry Water Model is known to be sufficient for constructing wave theories of sound through fluids.

As per dominant paradigm in fluid mechanics, many paradoxes arising in Euler's theory of fluids are attributed to the exclusion of viscosity. Challenging this "*unwarranted simplification*", Birkhoff argued that their root cause lies in the incompleteness of Euler's theory, inherent instability of steady flow, and the practice of using inadmissible eclectic pragmatic physical reasoning in place of "*deductive rigor*" among physicists and engineers. Recognition of the fallibility of "*rational hydrodynamics*" suggests the need "*to clarify the foundations of fluid mechanics.*" Further, in connection with D'Alembert's Paradox, Birkhoff advised the scientists to "*admit the possibility that a symmetrically stated problem may not have any stable symmetric solution*" (Birkhoff 1950). The historical background of disciplinary confrontation between mathematician Birkhoff and fluid dynamicists von Karman and Stoker has been analysed by Vincenti and David Bloor, the latter being the founder of the well-known 'strong program in sociology of scientific knowledge (SSK)' (Vincenti and Bloor 2003),

Heidelberger (Heidelberger 2006), and Ackerberg-Hastings and Grant (Ackerberg-Hastings and Grant 2020).

In his axiomatization of rational continuum mechanics, Noll (1958) proposed the concept of simple materials including simple fluids satisfying his axioms of constitutive equations (Malvern 1969; Ignatieff 1996; Benipal 1997). Noll's concept of simple fluids has been criticized later (Rivlin and Smith 1989; Benipal 2015).

Brenner has proposed a daring new bi-velocity theory of continuum fluid mechanics. As per Brenner, the continuity condition for mass conservation must be stated in terms of mass-based (Eulerian) mass-velocity v_m while fluid-based (Lagrangian) volume-velocity v_v of individual fluid particles must appear in Euler's equation the motion. These velocities are related by a constitutive equation proposed by him (Brenner 2003). It is argued by Kirtskhalia that the current theory of sound is applicable only to homogeneous pressure field. Ignoring the effect of entropy on the air density in the atmosphere and the lack of clarity about the concept of air incompressibility leads to incorrect formula for speed of sound at different altitudes. In the non-homogeneous pressure field in the presence of gravitational field, the sound wave is demonstrated to be a short-duration gravitational wave (Kirtskhalia 2022). Ivanov and Ivanova have established that the solutions of the second order partial differential wave equation stated in terms of velocity potential do not obey Euler's first order equations of motion and the continuity condition (Ivanov and Ivanova 2015).

A new constitutive equation for viscous stresses $\tau_{ij} = \frac{4}{3}\mu D_{kk}\delta_{ij} + 2\mu W_{ij}$ in Newtonian fluids is proposed Liu and Liu. Here, the viscous shear stress tensor, being proportional to the anti-symmetric vorticity tensor, turns out to be anti-symmetric (Liu and Liu, 2021). It is not clear whether the new constitutive equation satisfies the Principle of Material Frame Indifference in continuum mechanics (Truesdell and Rajagopal 2000). Recently, Taha, Gonzales, and Shorbagy have developed a new minimum principle for incompressible fluid mechanics (Taha, Gonzales, and Shorbagy 2023). Hughes and Gurung find it puzzling that satisfactory theoretical explanations have not yet been provided for the working of commonplace siphons (Hughes and Gurung 2014). Additionally, the siphonic connection between two points finite distance apart in a flow stream has not been understood from a natural philosophy perspective.

The essential tension between mathematical rigour of pure mathematics and exploitation of contingency in applied mathematics has been captured in the context of transonic aerodynamics (Vincenti and Bloor 2003) and D'Alembert's Paradox (Ackerberg-Hastings and Grant 2020). The divergence of the contentions of the Cambridge and Gottingen schools of thought on aerodynamic lift during the early twentieth century has been investigated by Bloor from the SSK perspective (Bloor 2011). The problem of lift has not yet been solved conclusively as new different theories of lift are currently being proposed (Hoffman, Jansson, and Johnson 2016; Gonzales and Taha 2023). It seems that, at its current stage of development, aerodynamics is largely an empirical discipline like medicine.

Due to their inherent nonlinearity, problems involving Navier-Stokes equations of incompressible Newtonian fluids obeying Stokes' condition have proved extremely difficult to solve. In fact, a Millennium Prize for establishing the existence and smoothness of their

solutions has been announced in 2000 by the Clay Mathematical Institute (Farwig 2020). Gibbon is curious to know whether the corresponding Euler Problem will be solved by 2257 full five centuries after the formulation of Euler equations (Gibbon 2008). In contrast, such paradoxes, critiques, or prizes are conspicuous by absence in Cauchy's theory of elasticity (1822) except the rari-multi-constant controversy which got resolved by mid-nineteenth century (Love 1892).

At this stage, a comparison of Euler's theory of inviscid fluids with Cauchy's theory of elasticity is instructive. To recapitulate, the state of stress at a point in a non-polar elastic solid is determined by the state of strain at that point. It can be observed that Euler's theory lacks the corresponding constitutive equation for pressure in terms of velocity as the primary kinematic variable. Instead, velocity-independent pressure field is invariably assumed to be determined by density field. For guaranteeing the assumed motion-independence of pressure, a controversial Stokes' condition (1845) is generally imposed on Newtonian fluids (Buresti 2015; Truesdell 1952). In Euler's dynamical equations of motion, pressure field is treated at par with external gravitational body force field. This explains the absence of Navier-like kinetic equations of motion and so of hyperbolic wave equations stated in terms of velocity field. This is also why the sound is conceptualised as a perturbation in the scalar pressure or density fields but not in the ambient velocity vector field. This lack of constitutive equation for pressure is carried over into Navier-Stokes equations for Newtonian fluids, Noll's simple fluids, and Reiner-Rivlin theory of non-Newtonian fluids (Malvern, 1969; Truesdell and Rajagopal 2000). Though pressure Hessian has been known to control the evolution of velocity gradient tensor (Gibbon 2008).

Euler's unified dynamical equations of motion stated in terms of pressure field are intended for all fluids. This unifying notion of fluids encompassing gases and liquids was not challenged in the axiomatization carried by Noll in his 1954 doctoral thesis entitled "On the Continuity of Solid and Fluid States of Matter" or in his theory of simple fluids (Malvern 1969; Ignatieff 1996). However, gases and liquids obey different equations of state. As temperature appears in their equation of state, gases exhibit inherently thermomechanical response. In contrast to gases, linear elastic liquids are characterised by their bulk modulus of linear elasticity K .

It has been observed by Truesdell and Rajagopal that the notion of fluid incompressibility applies only to liquids and is meaningless for gases (Truesdell and Rajagopal 2000). There is some confusion regarding the distinction between the incompressible fluids and incompressible flows. Incompressible fluids are defined by some restrictions on the material constants, while incompressible flows are characterised by the condition $D_{kk} = 0$ to be satisfied by the velocity field (Truesdell 1952). For incompressible liquids, the elastic bulk modulus $K = \infty$. Even for finite values of K , the elastic liquids are assumed to undergo only infinitesimally small elastic deformations resulting in practically constant density. The constitutive equation for elastic liquids $p = K\varepsilon_v$ is conspicuous by absence in textbooks as well as in majestic treatises on fluid mechanics. This is understandable as this equation belongs to isotropic linear elasticity wherein the volumetric strain ε_v is defined as divergence of the displacement field. Now, the concept of elastic displacements is meaningless for both liquids and gases lacking unique reference

state or placement relative to which the displacements are to be measured. For clarity, try think of displacement in the context of monsoon thunderstorms and river Ganges.

The gases are characterised by their adiabatic index $\gamma \geq 1$. Incompressible gases can be defined by the impossible condition $\gamma = 0$ in the equation of state $p = D\rho^\gamma$ implying the independence of pressure of density. Obviously, gases are inherently compressible. Some phenomena like free level surface, surface waves, surface tension, boiling, siphon action, water hammer, etc., are peculiar to liquids and meaningless for gases. In view of the above arguments, there is a clear need to construct dedicated theories of gas mechanics and liquid mechanics, earlier known carelessly as aerodynamics and hydrodynamics respectively.

From the short survey of the field presented above, it seems that pragmatic eclecticism reigns supreme in both the disciplines of fluid mechanics and acoustics. Physical arguments, experimentation, computation and now AI are invoked when required for specific contexts. Thus, there is need for formal consistent rational theories of fluid dynamics and acoustics.

Also, in place of the irrotational and equivoluminal elastic waves as perturbations in the displacement field, only the irrotational/longitudinal pressure wave is predicted to propagate through fluids. Since nobody has ever heard of transverse sound waves both literally and figuratively, these waves are absent from the discourse on acoustics. Obviously, there is no motivation for constructing a wave theory of such an apparently inadmissible sound. Still, existence of such transverse sound waves is proved in the present investigation though doing so was not its primary objective. The present investigation is not motivated even by the above critique of theories of fluid mechanics and acoustics.

There exist materials which are incapable of mobilising elastic resistance to full Cauchy stress tensor. Sub-Elasticity Theory is the unified theory of such sub-elastic materials, and the structures composed of such materials. Over the last three decades or so, this theory has been abstracted by the author from its applications to specific mechanical systems.

Sub-Elasticity Theory was conceived in author's doctoral thesis (Benipal 1992) wherein a theory of fully cracked concrete elastic structures was proposed based upon the Coignet-de Tedesko theory of flexure of reinforced concrete beam sections (1894). Such inherently nonlinear concrete structures as well as sagging elasto-flexible cables were shown to belong to the class of 'homogeneous mechanical systems'. Two early conference papers (Benipal 1993; Benipal 1994) out of this doctoral thesis dealt respectively with sagging elastic cables and concrete beams as homogeneous sub-elastic mechanical systems. Here, the configurational nonlinearity of cracked concrete beams is associated with shifting of the point of contraflexure under non-proportional loading. Thereafter, this theory was extended to cohesionless frictional materials (Benipal 1996) and perfectly plastic solids (Benipal 1998) both in a state of incipient failure. The unified theory of these underconstrained materials and structures lacking unique natural state was presented in the research monograph entitled "Configurational Mechanics". The quasi-static incremental constitutive equations of gaseous and liquid bodies in terms of normal stresses were derived (Benipal 2004).

A theory of isotropic linear bimodular elastic solids as first order homogeneous materials was proposed and applied to isotropically damaged solids (Raveendra Babu, Singh, and Benipal

2010). A theory of concrete beams as ‘first order homogeneous dynamical systems’ (Pandey and Benipal 2017) and a dynamical theory of sagging elasto-flexible cables (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016) were constructed later by the author and co-workers. Research on theoretical concrete mechanics conducted by the author and the doctoral students supervised and co-supervised by him is summarized (Benipal and Sharma 2021). In this research monograph, the methodology of constructing an abstract theory from particular mechanical systems is presented in the Preface ‘An Abstraction Called Concrete’.

To distinguish the proposed unified theory from the well-known ‘configurational mechanics’ field dealing with configurational forces and from the apparently similar hypoelasticity theory, the same theory is renamed here as Sub-Elasticity Theory. Like these sub-elastic mechanical systems, fluids too lack unique natural state. The *suo moto* intention of the author to explore the mechanics of gases and liquids as distinct sub-elastic states of matter provided the sufficient motivation for the present research undertaking.

The present paper is divided into two parts: In this first part, a new sub-elastic wave theory of sound predicting both longitudinal and transverse waves is presented. In place of Euler’s point-theoretic approach, a body-theoretic Sub-Elasticity approach is deemed to be more appropriate for capturing the variability of configuration as geometric aspect of the state of gases and liquids. Here, a rectangular parallelepipedon subjected to normal compressive forces is chosen to represent the material body as the object of reference. Its side lengths determined by applied forces define the equilibrium state configuration of the material body. The relationship between the body dimensions and the equilibrated forces is proposed as an alternative version of the equation of state for gases and incompressible liquids.

Using these equations of state for material bodies, rate-type constitutive equations are derived. In place of well-known Euler dynamical equations of motion stated in terms of pressure, new Cauchy-like dynamical equations of motion stated in terms of stress rate tensor components are formulated. Further, Navier-type kinetic equations of motion and hyperbolic wave equations are obtained with velocity vector as primary kinematic variable. These new hyperbolic wave equations are used to derive the expressions for speeds of irrotational/longitudinal and equivoluminal/transverse waves propagating through liquids and gases. The scope of the proposed barotropic theory is restricted to mechanical response of liquids and gases though gases require proper thermomechanical formulation. Implications of the present paper to fluid mechanics, acoustics, and the philosophy of science are critically evaluated in the accompanying second part of the paper (Benipal 2026).

2. Sub-Elasticity Theory

The static and dynamic behavior of two-node 4-DOF perfectly flexible sagging elastic planar cable structures has been investigated by (Benipal 1993; Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016). Their configuration-defining nodal coordinates, nodal elastic displacements, and elastic strain energy are functions homogeneous of order zero, one and two of the nodal forces respectively. In contrast, their configurational energy turns out to be first order homogeneous function of the forces. Thus, in the absence of forces, the passive state configuration of both inextensible and

elastically deformable cables turns out to be indeterminate. Under proportional loading, their configuration remains invariant and the system experiences only elastic displacements. In contrast, general non-proportional loading causes the sub-elastic elasto-configurational system to exhibit both configurational and elastic response.

Thus, there exists, corresponding to each equilibrium state, a unique natural state configuration accessible by proportional unloading from that equilibrium state. This natural state also plays the role of a reference state for defining their elastic displacements. For example, unlike gaseous bodies, the elastic liquid bodies undergo small elastic displacements. Upon unloading in an arbitrary manner, their natural state is determined by their relative magnitudes when the last traces of applied forces are removed. This explains their lack of unique passive natural reference state.

Change of configuration under non-proportional loading causes configurational nonlinearity and is associated with the force-dependence of natural configuration. The configurational nonlinearity is distinct from both the material nonlinearity associated with nonlinear stress-strain relation of the material and the geometric nonlinearity associated with its finite elastic deformations. Configurational nonlinearity is exhibited even by cable structures made of linear elastic materials undergoing infinitesimally small elastic deformations. Configurational response is the only response displayed both by the elastically inextensible cables and the incompressible liquids. The reversible constitutive equations for cables are of rate-type wherein the nodal loading rates are linear functions of the nodal velocities and the tangent stiffness matrix coefficients depend upon current nodal loads apart from material elasticity. Consequently, the third order nonlinear differential equation of motion governs their nonlinear dynamic response (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016). This new theory of sagging elastic cables proposed by Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal is validated with available experimental data (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal, 2022). It has been argued by the present author that the third order nonlinear differential equation is the proper equation of motion describing matrix dynamics of all MDOF nonlinear elastic structures (Benipal 2019).

To reiterate the assertion from the Introduction, the behavior of sagging elastic cables resembles that of elastic liquid bodies in many respects: Unlike elastically undeformable or rigid solids, both elastically inextensible cables and incompressible liquids do exhibit rich mechanical response because of their configurational variability under the load variations. Like flexible sagging cables, the oceans and Earth's atmosphere respectively as liquid and gaseous bodies are experienced in their equilibrium state configurations uniquely determined by the ubiquitous and ever-present gravitational field. Like equilibrated loads on sagging cables and tensile force in stretched cables, instantaneous pressure provides stiffness to gases and liquids.

Generally, the response of cable structures to additional applied loads is predicted by assigning initial configuration and stiffness matrix as determined by the gravitational forces. In contrast, in the proposed theory (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016), the gravitational forces are not accorded with such a privileged status but are treated at par with other applied forces. Thus, the problem caused by absence of unique passive natural state and stiffness matrix is confronted and solved. The same approach is followed here for gaseous and liquid bodies. In this manner, rational mechanics transcends the phenomenological nature of experience and experiment. All

experimentation is conducted properly by overcoming the phenomenological connection under the guidance of rational physical theories. After all, experimental observations constitute the physical solution of the mathematical initial/boundary value problems formulated in the physical theory.

In contrast to elastic solids, elastic liquids are characterized by definite compression bulk modulus, but vanishing shear modulus and tension bulk modulus. Similarly, in contrast to elastic bars, elasto-flexible cables possess definite elastic resistance to axial tensile force but no elastic resistance to axial compressive force, flexural shear force, and flexural moment. Thus, both elastic cables ($E_t \neq E_c = 0$) and liquids $K_c \neq K_t = 0$ are bimodular and lack central symmetry. What are the implications of the purely attractive nature of gravitational forces in contrast to electrostatic and magnetostatic forces which can be attractive and repulsive? As a matter of fact, the modes of operation of attractive and repulsive forces in electrostatics and magnetostatics are known to be utterly different.

Further, the constitutive equation for any point on the sagging elastic cables stated as $F = EA\varepsilon$ does not exhibit configurational response characteristic of sagging cable structures. Similarly, equations of state $p = K\varepsilon_v$ and $p = D\rho^{\gamma}$ respectively for liquid and gaseous material points do not reveal anything about configuration of material bodies. Even sagging cables under a single point load P do not experience any change in configuration as a single load can vary only proportionally: αP where $\alpha \geq 0$. Similarly, consider a liquid parallelepipedon under one independently varying force P_1 and with the two constant dimensions a_2 and a_3 . This body cannot experience any change in configuration upon variation of P_1 . It seems that, in Boyle's experiments (1642), the gas pressure was varied by varying only one force. The concept of scalar gas pressure is very limiting in contrast to the concept of force vector with three independently varying components which are capable of non-proportional variation affecting configurational variation.

These observations suggested to the author the choice of liquid and gaseous bodies as appropriate objects of reference in place of material points. It is this Cable Structures - Liquid Bodies Analogy which has motivated this research investigation. Then, the sub-elasticity theory of liquid bodies was extended naturally to gaseous bodies.

Cauchy's concept of stress tensor (1822) generalizes the earlier concepts of hydrostatic pressure in fluids, normal stresses in elastic bars, axial tension in flexible cables, Newtonian shear stresses in viscous fluids, and Coulomb's shear stresses in cohesive-frictional materials (Truesdell 1968). Cauchy's theory of fully elastic solids succeeded the earlier theories of sub-elastic states of matter like fluids, cables, and granular materials. Elastic solids possess a unique passive natural state which also plays the role of reference state for defining elastic displacements. In contrast, the above sub-elastic states of matter lack such unique passive natural reference state. With the conceptual development of the material capability of elastic resistance to the full set of Cauchy stress tensor components, the concept of configuration associated with sub-elastic material bodies vanished from the post-Cauchy discourse. The fact that Cauchy's fully elastic solids possess unique passive natural reference state justifies the choice of material point lacking any configuration-related attributes as the object of reference.

In the context of historical development of classical mechanics, Sub-Elasticity Theory is observed to belong to the pre-Cauchy era as it deals with such elastically under-constrained mechanical systems as perfectly flexible cables, pendula, cohesionless granular materials, liquids, gases, etc., (Benipal 2004).

Endowed with two elastic constants, viz., bulk and shear moduli, solids can mobilize elastic resistance to all components of Cauchy stress tensor and solid bodies possess definite volume and unique passive natural reference state configuration (Love 1892). Liquids are characterized by only one elastic constant, viz., the bulk modulus, and possess unique volume but lack unique natural configuration. Gases lack any elastic resistance and so possess neither definite volume nor unique configuration in their natural state. The different equations of state of gases and liquids represent their different modes of resistance to pressure. To distinguish them from the fully elastic solid state, liquids and gases with partial elastic resistance are called sub-elastic states of matter. For the isotropic linear elastic solid, the elastic moduli $3K$ and $2G$ turn out to be eigenvalues of the coefficient matrix relating 'normal stress vector' with 'normal strain vector'. The corresponding eigenvectors pertain respectively to the dilatational and distortional modes of deformation. In view of this, solids, liquids, and gases can be identified as the eigenstates of matter.

Upon melting, both shear and tension bulk moduli vanish while even the compression bulk modulus vanishes upon boiling. Perhaps the latent heats of fusion and evaporation are related to the magnitudes of these vanishing bulk and shear moduli respectively. Assuming the nominal value of density $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the latent heat of evaporation of water is 2260 kJ/kg or $2260 * 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$. Here, the units N/m^2 of elastic moduli are interpreted as units of energy $\text{N} - \text{m/m}^3$ or J/m^3 just like pressure p is interpreted as energy in Daniel Bernoulli's theorem. The bulk modulus of water equals 2.2 GPa or $2200 * 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$, a value much lesser than the bulk modulus 3.85 GPa or $3850 * 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$ of ice. Indeed, the latent heat of evaporation water turns out to be equal to its bulk modulus!!! Further, the latent heats of fusion of water equals 334 kJ/kg or $334 * 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$. However, the shear modulus of ice is about 2.3 GPa or $2300 * 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3$ a value much higher than its latent heats of fusion. Recall that melting of ice is associated with vanishing its tension bulk modulus as well. Better explanation needs to be offered for the correspondence, if any, between the elastic and thermodynamic properties.

Further, speeds of longitudinal and transverse sound waves in bubble-free ice are 3838 m/s and 1826 m/s respectively (Vogt, Laihem, and Weibusch, 2008). It is observed that speed of transverse waves in ice is slightly higher than the speed (1543 m/s) of longitudinal waves through water. This observation is compatible with the fact that the shear modulus of ice and the bulk modulus of water are approximately equal.

It should be noted that the concept of configuration representing the geometric aspects, like size and shape, of the state pertains only to material bodies, not to dimensionless material points. The bodies composed of liquids and gases do possess unique equilibrium state when subjected to forces introducing only the admissible state of hydrostatic pressure. When subjected to additional applied forces introducing inadmissible state of stress in their current equilibrium configuration, these bodies respond by instantaneously changing their

configuration to attain a new equilibrium configuration supporting only the admissible state of stress. Continuous temporal variation of applied forces results in continuous variation of the equilibrium configuration. In the equilibrium states corresponding to the instantaneous values of varying forces, the material continues to be subjected to only the admissible states of total stress. In contrast, here the force rates are assumed to introduce the full set of Cauchy stress rates in the material. Thus, the material can sustain both the admissible and the inadmissible stress rates but only the admissible total state of stress (Benipal 2004).

For visualizing the above scenario, consider a parallelepipedon made of perfectly plastic von Mises solid in a state of incipient yielding under uniaxial compressive force. Application of an additional compressive force of finite magnitude in the same direction causes plastic flow which continues till a new state of equilibrium is reached under the new total compressive force. Thus, as shown by the present author (Benipal 1998), the body returns to its state of incipient yielding by changing its equilibrium configuration by increasing its area resisting the increased force. It must be appreciated that it is only under uniaxial compression that such a body exhibits stable plastic response. In contrast, under uniaxial tensile force, no new state of plastic equilibrium state exists, and the body exhibits instability failure by necking, etc.

Equilibrium configurations of sub-elastic material bodies are determined by the instantaneous total and relative magnitudes of equilibrated applied forces. Stated mathematically, the configuration-defining dimensions are functions homogeneous of certain order of the applied forces. Consequently, their elastic displacements, if any, as well as configurational and elastic energy potentials are also homogeneous functions of the same forces. Thus, sub-elastic material bodies belong to the class of inherently nonlinear reversible Homogeneous Mechanical Systems. Linear elastic mechanical systems belong, though merely vacuously, to the class of First Order Homogeneous Mechanical Systems.

The body-theoretic Sub-Elasticity Theory is implemented here for liquid and gaseous bodies as follows: A rectangular parallelepipedon with dimensions a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 under the action of applied normal compressive forces P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 acting respectively along corresponding dimensions is chosen as the object of study. The quantity of material in the parallelepipedon is measured by its specified mass. The normal surface tractions applied upon the surfaces of this homogeneously stressed body equal the normal stresses acting within the body: $t_{n1} = \sigma_{11} = \frac{P_1}{a_2 a_3}$, $t_{n2} = \sigma_{22} = \frac{P_2}{a_3 a_1}$, $t_{n3} = \sigma_{33} = \frac{P_3}{a_1 a_2}$. As both the liquids and gases can sustain only hydrostatic pressure, one obtains $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{22} = \sigma_{33} = p$. Using the relevant equation of state and knowing $a_1 a_2 a_3 = V$, one obtains unique reversible relations between the applied normal forces and the equilibrium state dimensions of the parallelepipedon. The forces are homogeneous functions $P_i(a_1, a_2, a_3)$ of the body dimensions and vice versa as $a_i(P_1, P_2, P_3)$. These force-dimension relations represent alternative statements of the equations of state for the material. Using these relations, equivalent rate-type versions of the equations of state are also derived. Stated in terms of tangent stiffness and flexibility matrices for the body $K_{ij} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial a_j}$ and $f_{ij} = \frac{\partial a_i}{\partial P_j}$, the rate-type constitutive equations take the form $\dot{P}_i = K_{ij} \dot{a}_j$ or $\dot{a}_i = f_{ij} \dot{P}_j$.

From these rate-type constitutive force-dimension equations for the material body, stress rate - rate of stretching constitutive equations are deduced for the generic material point. These constitutive equations resemble linear isotropic tensor functions like stress-strain constitutive equations for the isotropic linear elastic solids undergoing small elastic displacements stated using Lamé's constants. Here, the coefficients corresponding to Lamé's constants are determined by the material constants in addition to instantaneous pressure.

For different classes of gases, the material constant is the adiabatic index $\gamma \geq 1$. From the kinetic-statistical theory of gases, the discrete values of γ for monoatomic, diatomic, and triatomic gases respectively are well-known to be $5/3$, $7/5$, and $4/3$ or equivalently 1.67, 1.40 and 1.33. Its value for each mixture of gases is also constant, e. g., 1.4 for air. Each linear elastic liquid has a different material constant, i. e., the bulk modulus K . For the special cases of isothermal gases ($\gamma = 1$) and incompressible liquids ($K = \infty$), the Lamé-like coefficients depend only on instantaneous pressure. Material density is a material parameter along with bulk modulus for liquids, while it is a response variable for gases.

Inserting the expressions for stress rate tensor in the rate-type Cauchy-type dynamical equations of motion, one obtains new Navier-type kinetic equations of motion stated only in terms of the spatial and temporal partial derivatives of the primary kinematic velocity vector field. From these kinetic equations, hyperbolic wave equations are derived yielding the expressions for irrotational and equivoluminal wave speeds for liquids and gases. Explicit formulation of Sub-Elasticity Theory of gases and liquids is presented below.

From a mathematical perspective, physically defined sub-elastic systems belong to the class of homogeneous mechanical systems. This is because their configuration defining parameters, elastic displacements, if any, tangent flexibility configurational/elastic matrix coefficients, and configurational potentials are function homogeneous of some order of the equilibrated forces. In view of this, theory of homogeneous functions is summarized here.

A dependent variable Z representing a scalar or a vector component Z_i is a homogeneous function of order m of the independent variables q_j if $Z = q_1^m f\left(\frac{q_2}{q_1}, \frac{q_3}{q_1}\right)$. For such functions, the algebraic relation $Z(\alpha q_1, \alpha q_2, \alpha q_3) = \alpha^m Z(q_1, q_2, q_3)$ holds. Positively homogeneous mechanical systems ($\alpha \geq 0$) lack central symmetry under load reversal. Thus, $Z(-q_1, -q_2, -q_3) \neq -Z(q_1, q_2, q_3)$. Clearly, all sub-elastic systems are positively homogeneous mechanical systems.

Euler theorems for homogeneous functions are stated as $\frac{\partial Z}{\partial q_j} q_j = mZ$ for scalar Z . For vector components, it gives $\frac{\partial Z_i}{\partial q_j} q_j = mZ_i$ or $N_{ij} q_j = mZ_i$ where $N_{ij} = \frac{\partial Z_i}{\partial q_j}$ represents the tangent matrix. Alternatively, $S_{ij} q_j = Z_i$ where the secant matrix is determined as $S_{ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{m}$. In case, Z_i and q_j represent elastic displacements u_i and loads P_j , the total and rate-type constitutive equations are obtained as $u_i = S_{ij} P_j$ and $\dot{u}_i = N_{ij} \dot{P}_j$. Like linear systems, for inherently nonlinear first order homogeneous mechanical systems ($m = 1$) also, the secant and tangent flexibility matrices are identical. As a matter of fact, linear elastic structures belong, though

vacuously, to the class of first order homogeneous mechanical systems. In case $Z(q_1, q_2)$ is a homogeneous function of two variables, Euler's second theorem applies:

$$q_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial q_1^2} + 2q_1 q_2 \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial q_1 \partial q_2} + q_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial q_2^2} = m(m-1)Z$$

According to Brickell, when $Z_i(q_1, q_2, q_3)$ are homogeneous functions of order m , their partial derivatives $\frac{\partial Z_i}{\partial q_j}$ are homogeneous functions of order $(m-1)$. This is why the tangent flexibility matrix coefficients N_{ij} are homogeneous functions of order $(m-1)$ and the energy potentials are homogeneous functions of order $(m+1)$. Further, Brickell's theorem (Brickell 1967) states that the energy potential $\Omega = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$ of homogeneity order $m \geq 2$ is a homogeneous quadratic polynomial if the matrix of coefficients $g_{ij} = \frac{\partial^2(\Omega/2)}{\partial q^i \partial q^j}$ is positive definite and the Riemannian metric $g_{ij}dq^i dq^j$ has zero curvature.

Recall that strain (complementary) energy of linear elastic solids are second order homogeneous functions of the strain (stress) tensor components. As a matter of fact, thermodynamics potentials are homogeneous functions of relevant variables. The roots of normal polynomial equations are first order homogeneous functions of the coefficients. For example, the roots, y_1 and y_2 , of the normal quadratic equation cast in the form $y^2 + by + c^2 = 0$ are first order homogeneous functions of coefficients b and c .

3. Sub-Elasticity Theory of Inviscid Gases: Theoretical Gas Mechanics and Acoustics

3.1 General Case: Adiabatic Barotropic Gases

For the gaseous parallelepipedon under normal forces P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 , the classical Laplace adiabatic equation of state (1816) for the gases $pV^\gamma = C$ and $V = a_1 a_2 a_3$ can be recast in the following three equivalent forms:

$$P_1 a_1 = P_2 a_2 = P_3 a_3 = \frac{C}{V^{\gamma-1}} = pV$$

$$P_1 a_1 V^{\gamma-1} = P_2 a_2 V^{\gamma-1} = P_3 a_3 V^{\gamma-1} = C$$

$$P_1 a_1^\gamma a_2^{\gamma-1} a_3^{\gamma-1} = P_2 a_1^{\gamma-1} a_2^\gamma a_3^{\gamma-1} = P_3 a_1^{\gamma-1} a_2^{\gamma-1} a_3^\gamma = C$$

The normal forces acting on the parallelepipedon are determined uniquely as $P_i = a_i^{-(3\gamma-2)} C \left(\frac{a_j}{a_i}\right)^{\gamma-1} \left(\frac{a_k}{a_i}\right)^{\gamma-1}$. The equivalent relation $P_i(a_1, a_2, a_3) = a_i^{-(3\gamma-2)} f\left(\frac{a_j}{a_i}, \frac{a_k}{a_i}\right)$ implies that the forces P_i acting on the rectangular parallelepipedon are functions homogeneous of the order $-(3\gamma-2)$ of its dimensions (a_1, a_2, a_3) . The symmetric tangent stiffness matrix $K_{ij} = \frac{\partial P_i}{\partial a_j}$ used in the incremental constitutive relation stated as $dP_i = K_{ij} da_j$ for the rectangular parallelepipedon is obtained as $K_{ij} = -(\gamma-1 + \delta_{ij}) \frac{P_i}{a_j}$. Using Euler's theorem for homogeneous functions, the following theorem for adiabatic equation of state of gases is

proved: $\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial a_j} a_j = K_{ij} a_j = -(3\gamma - 2)P_i$. In this manner, another alternative total version of the Laplace equation of state (1816) of the gaseous body is obtained.

The above constitutive relation $dP_i = K_{ij} da_j$ is restated in the equivalent universal normalised rate form as $\frac{\dot{P}_i}{P_i} = G_{ij} \frac{\dot{a}_j}{a_j}$ where $G_{ij} = -(\gamma - 1 + \delta_{ij})$ with constant matrix components. The eigenvalues of the matrix G_{ij} turn out to be $(-(3\gamma - 2), -1, -1)$. The distinct eigenvalue corresponds to the proportional loading rate eigenvector ($\dot{P}_1/P_1 = \dot{P}_2/P_2 = \dot{P}_3/P_3$) and the purely dilatational mode ($\dot{a}_1/a_1 = \dot{a}_2/a_2 = \dot{a}_3/a_3$). In contrast, the remaining two equal eigenvalues correspond to an orthogonal eigenvector ($\dot{P}_1/P_1 + \dot{P}_2/P_2 + \dot{P}_3/P_3 = 0$) and an equivoluminal mode ($\dot{a}_1/a_1 + \dot{a}_2/a_2 + \dot{a}_3/a_3 = 0$) or ($\dot{V} = 0$). This equivoluminal mode of motion implies the invariance of the volume $a_1 a_2 a_3 = V$ and correspondingly of the triple product $P_1 P_2 P_3$ of applied forces. Thus, the volume change occurs only as and when the triple product $P_1 P_2 P_3$ varies.

Using the equality $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = p$ between the principal stresses and pressure, the above equation can be restated in terms of principal stress rate tensor $\dot{\sigma}_i$ and principal rate of stretching tensor components $D_i = \dot{a}_i/a_i$ as $\dot{\sigma}_i = g_{ij} D_j$ where $g_{ij} = -(\gamma - 1 + \delta_{ij})p$. The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the adiabatic gas matrix g_{ij} are obtained as $(-(3\gamma - 2)p, -p, -p)$. The distinct eigenvalue implies flow characterized by $D_1 = D_2 = D_3$ caused by $\dot{\sigma}_1 = \dot{\sigma}_2 = \dot{\sigma}_3$. For the parallelepipedon, this eigenvector corresponds to proportional loading and purely dilatational mode. Positive proportional stress rates, or equivalently the negative rate of change of pressure, causes rate of dilatation provided the eigenvalue $(-(3\gamma - 2)p)$ is positive. This confirms the conventional expectation that pressure as compressive stress must always be of negative sense. Otherwise, an increasing pressure will be accompanied by dilatation – an absurd inference. The remaining two equal eigenvalues correspond to the isochoric flow characterized by $D_1 + D_2 + D_3 = 0$ caused by purely deviatoric stress rates $\dot{\sigma}_1 + \dot{\sigma}_2 + \dot{\sigma}_3 = 0$. This latter mode does not result in any change in pressure and density.

The above constitutive equations relating principal stress rate - rate of stretching tensors resemble those relating principal stress-strain equations for isotropic linear elastic solids. For such solids, the same constitutive equations express the normal stress – normal strain relations from which the shear stress - strain relations can be derived. This is so because here the normal stresses are linear functions of the normal strains, while the shear stresses are proportional to the corresponding shear strains. Using this solid - gas/liquid analogy, the following general stress rate – rate of stretching constitutive equations for gases are deduced from the principal rate-type constitutive equations for the gases derived above.

In reference to the principal coordinate system, the above constitutive equation can also be stated as $\dot{\sigma}_i = -(\gamma - 1)p(D_1 + D_2 + D_3) - pD_i$. Here, $(D_1 + D_2 + D_3)$ represents the rate of dilatation. Replacing $\dot{\sigma}_i$ and D_i with $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and D_{ij} respectively, one gets the corresponding constitutive equation stated in reference to an arbitrary cartesian coordinate system. In terms of the general stress rate and rate of stretching tensors, $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and D_{ij} , the sub-elastic adiabatic rate-type constitutive equation is stated as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = -(\gamma - 1)pD_{kk}\delta_{ij} - pD_{ij}$. Thus, the stress rate

tensor is expressed as an isotropic linear tensor function of instantaneous rate of stretching tensor. This constitutive equation resembles the constitutive equation $\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \varepsilon_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \varepsilon_{ij}$ for isotropic linear elastic solids stated in terms of stress and strain tensors. The coefficients corresponding to the Lamé's constants are identified as $\lambda \equiv -(\gamma - 1)p$ and $2\mu \equiv -p$. This gives $\lambda + 2\mu \equiv -\gamma p$ and $\mu \equiv -\frac{p}{2}$. Alternatively, the constitutive equations can be stated in terms of deviatoric rate of stretching tensor as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = -\frac{(3\gamma-2)}{3} p D_{kk} \delta_{ij} - p D'_{ij}$.

After deriving constitutive equations for the gases, the dynamical and kinetic equations of motion as well as wave equations are formulated as follows. The rate-type version of the familiar Cauchy's dynamical law of motion stated as $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + \dot{b}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \frac{D(v_i)}{Dt})$ in terms of stress rates and material time derivative of the velocity field is adopted for gases and liquids. For the purpose of illustration, the equation of motion $\frac{\partial \sigma_{11}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{21}}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{31}}{\partial x_3} + \dot{b}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \frac{D(v_1)}{Dt})$ is stated explicitly along x_1 -axis,. Using the definitions $D_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i})$ and $D_{kk} = \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial v_3}{\partial x_3}$, this equation reduces to $-(\gamma - \frac{1}{2}) p \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_1} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_1 + \dot{b}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \frac{D(v_1)}{Dt})$. Following the same line of argument, one obtains the following general Navier-like kinetic equations of motion stated in terms of the primary kinematic velocity field: $-(\gamma - \frac{1}{2}) p \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i + \dot{b}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \frac{D(v_i)}{Dt})$.

For the case of constant body forces field, the term \dot{b}_i vanishes. For small flow velocities, velocity gradients, and small density variation, the dynamical equation of motion attains the following simpler form: $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$. The kinematic term $\frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ on the right-hand side of the equation denotes the rate of acceleration *aka* 'jerk'. This new dynamical equation of motion replaces the Euler's dynamical equation of motion $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = \rho \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t}$. For this special case, the general Navier-like kinetic equations of motion stated in terms of the primary kinematic velocity field is derived as $-(\gamma - \frac{1}{2}) p \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ where $i=1, 2, 3$. Here, by the phrase 'kinetic equations of motion' including material constants is meant that the spatial velocity field determines its temporal evolution. This contrasts with the Euler dynamical equations of motion for fluids stated in terms of pressure field but without material constants.

For irrotational motion $\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i}$ and so $\frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} = \nabla^2 v_i$, the following hyperbolic wave equation is obtained: $-\gamma p \nabla^2 v_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ or $\nabla^2 v_i = \frac{1}{c_1^2} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ giving the irrotational wave speed $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma p}{\rho}}$.

Thus, the well-known formula for speed of arial longitudinal sound wave has been derived using sub-elastic wave theory. Further, for equivoluminal motion, $D_{kk} = 0$, one gets the wave equation $\nabla^2 v_i = -\frac{2\rho}{p} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{c_2^2} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$, thus giving the expression for equivoluminal wave speed as $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$. These expressions for the irrotational and equivoluminal sound waves could have

been directly obtained from the expressions $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda+2\mu}{\rho}}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\rho}}$ stated in terms of Lamé's constants. The arial sound wave speeds are obtained as $c_1 = 331.2m/s$ and $c_2 = 197.6m/s$. The irrotational waves propagate at different speeds through homogeneous monoatomic, diatomic, triatomic gases or their mixtures, while speed of the newly predicted equivoluminal/transverse waves is same through all gases or their mixtures like air.

Because of the equivalence between the adiabatic equation of state for gases with the Lane-Emden-Fowler equation (Herman 2023), the theory of gases proposed herein can be employed in astrophysics for determining the structure of polytropic stars.

3.2 Special Case: Isothermal Barotropic Gases

The isothermal equation of state for all gaseous bodies $pV = C = RT$, also known as Boyle's law (1662), is obtained from the adiabatic equation of state as a special case ($\gamma = 1$). This equation of state yields its alternative versions as $P_1 a_1 = P_2 a_2 = P_3 a_3 = pV = C = RT$. The forces are inversely proportional to the corresponding dimensions. The tangent stiffness matrix is defined as $\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial a_j} = K_{ij} = -\frac{C}{a_j^2} \delta_{ij}$ in the rate-type universal equation $\dot{P}_i = K_{ij} \dot{a}_j$ or equivalently $\dot{P}_i = -\frac{C}{a_i^2} \dot{a}_i$. Thus, both the total and rate-type responses of the gaseous body are uncoupled in that an applied force causes the response only in its own direction. Equivalently stated, though merely vacuously, forces are -1 order homogeneous functions of the body dimensions. Thus, one obtains the universal relation $\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial a_j} a_j = -P_i$. The above universal relation is restated below in rate-type normalised universal equation as $\dot{P}_i/P_i = G_{ij} \dot{a}_j/a_j$ where the universal gas matrix $G_{ij} = -\delta_{ij}$. All the eigenvalues (-1, -1, -1) of G_{ij} in this equation turn out to be equal. Thus, new total and rate-type versions of Boyle's law (1662) are derived.

In terms of stress-rate and rate of stretching tensors, the above rate-type matrix equation can be stated as $\dot{\sigma}_i = g_{ij} D_j$ where $g_{ij} = -p\delta_{ij}$. Eigenvalue analysis of the universal gas matrix g_{ij} reveals all the three eigenvalues ($-p, -p, -p$) to be equal. The corresponding eigenvectors are $(\dot{\sigma}_1, 0, 0)$, $(0, \dot{\sigma}_2, 0)$ and $(0, 0, \dot{\sigma}_3)$ and $(D_1, 0, 0)$, $(0, D_2, 0)$ and $(0, 0, D_3)$. Each of these principal stress rates, for example $\dot{\sigma}_1$, results in corresponding volumetric strain change rate $D_1 = \frac{\dot{a}_1}{a_1} = \frac{\dot{a}_1 a_2 a_3}{a_1 a_2 a_3} = \frac{\dot{V}}{V}$. From the constitutive equation $\dot{\sigma}_i = -p D_i$ in reference to the principal coordinate system, the constitutive equation in reference to general coordinate system is obtained as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = -p D_{ij}$. Thus, the Lamé's constants turn out to be $\lambda \equiv 0$ and $2\mu \equiv -p$. As above, this yields the Navier-like equations of motion as $-\frac{p}{2} \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$.

For irrotational motion, one obtains the hyperbolic wave equation: $\nabla^2 v_i = -\frac{\rho}{p} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ giving the expression $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{\rho}}$ for irrotational/longitudinal wave speed. Further, for equivoluminal motion, one gets the wave equation $\nabla^2 v_i = -\frac{2\rho}{p} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$, thus giving the expression for

equivoluminal/transverse wave speed as $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$. These expressions for the wave speeds are universal being valid for all the gases in isothermal motion. The expression for the irrotational wave speed c_1 is identical with the Newton's well-known expression for longitudinal sound wave speed. However, the equivoluminal 'transverse' waves are predicted to propagate at the same speed c_2 both for adiabatic and isothermal motions.

4 Sub-Elasticity Theory of Inviscid Liquids: Theoretical Liquid Mechanics and Acoustics

4.1 Special Case: Elastically Incompressible Liquids

Amount of liquid in the body is measured by its mass as well as by its volume as the density of the liquids is constant irrespective of the state of motion. This holds for elastic liquids as well because the infinitesimally small volumetric strain causes only negligible change in their volume and so in their density. For a parallelepipedon composed of an incompressible liquid of specified definite volume V , one gets $P_1 a_1 = P_2 a_2 = P_3 a_3 = pV$. These equalities represent the universal total equations of state for incompressible liquids with invariant volume V . The following expressions for body dimensions are derived in terms of applied forces:

$$a_1 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_2 P_3}{P_1 P_1}} V \quad a_2 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_3 P_1}{P_2 P_2}} V \quad a_3 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_1 P_2}{P_3 P_3}} V$$

The body dimensions are zero order homogeneous functions of the equilibrated forces and the tangent flexibility matrix coefficients are given as $\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial P_j} = A_{ij} = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3} \frac{a_i}{P_j}$. Application of Euler's theorem yields $\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial P_j} P_j = A_{ij} P_j = 0$. This implies that the flexibility matrix A_{ij} is singular and the tangent stiffness matrix K_{ij} cannot be obtained by inverting it. This implies that the equilibrated forces cannot be determined uniquely by the liquid body dimensions.

This yields universal rate-type equations for the body as $\dot{a}_i/a_i = F_{ij} \dot{P}_j/P_j$ where $F_{ij} = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3}$ represents the universal tangent flexibility matrix. The eigenvalues of the universal liquid flexibility matrix F_{ij} in the above equation turn out to be (0, -1, -1). The vanishing distinct eigenvalue corresponds to proportional loading eigenvector ($\dot{P}_1/P_1 = \dot{P}_2/P_2 = \dot{P}_3/P_3$) and ($\dot{a}_1/a_1 = \dot{a}_2/a_2 = \dot{a}_3/a_3$) The other two equal eigenvalues correspond to orthogonal eigenvectors satisfying the conditions ($\dot{P}_1/P_1 + \dot{P}_2/P_2 + \dot{P}_3/P_3 = 0$) and ($\dot{a}_1/a_1 + \dot{a}_2/a_2 + \dot{a}_3/a_3 = 0$).

Using the definitions of stress rates and rates of stretching presented for gases, expressions for configurational rates of stretching D_{ic} are given as $D_{ic} = l_{ij} \dot{\sigma}_j$ where $l_{ij} = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3p}$. Eigenvalue analysis of the universal liquid matrix l_{ij} reveals eigenvalues as $(0, \frac{-1}{p}, \frac{-1}{p})$ associated with the following corresponding eigenvectors:

$$\lambda_1 = 0: \quad \dot{\sigma}_1 = \dot{\sigma}_2 = \dot{\sigma}_3 \quad D_{1c} = D_{2c} = D_{3c}$$

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \frac{-1}{p}; \quad \dot{\sigma}_1 + \dot{\sigma}_2 + \dot{\sigma}_3 = 0 \quad D_{1c} + D_{2c} + D_{3c} = 0$$

It can be observed that, as per the first eigenvector, the proportional force variations introduce only change in pressure. As this eigenvalue vanishes, the body suffers no change in its dimensions. This conclusion can be inferred from the fact stated above that the dimensions of the incompressible liquid body in equilibrium with applied normal forces are zero order homogeneous functions of these forces. In other words, the body dimensions are determined by the relative, not absolute, magnitudes of the applied forces. In the absence of forces, the body dimensions are indeterminate. This implies that the liquid body lacks unique passive state configuration. Liquids in their passive state ($p = 0$) are infinitely compliant as the coefficients of the compliance matrix l_{ij} attain infinitely high values. The remaining two equal eigenvalues correspond to deviatoric stress rates resulting in invariance of pressure. In all the cases, the body volume remains invariant for the incompressible liquids.

4.2 General Case: Elastically Compressible Liquids

Under hydrostatic pressure, linear elastic liquids experience volumetric elastic strain equal to $\varepsilon_v = p/K$. The linear elastic strain along any dimension of the parallelepipedon is given by $p/3K$. The infinitesimally small elastic displacement u_i in any direction turns out to be $u_i = pa_i/3K$. Inserting the expressions for p and a_i in this expression for u_i , one obtains the expressions for u_i in terms of applied forces. For example, $u_i = P_i a_i^2/3KV$ as $p = P_i a_i/V$.

Alternatively, $u_1 = \frac{P_1}{3KV} \left[\frac{P_2 P_3}{P_1 P_1} V \right]^{2/3}$ $u_2 = \frac{P_2}{3KV} \left[\frac{P_3 P_1}{P_2 P_2} V \right]^{2/3}$ $u_3 = \frac{P_3}{3KV} \left[\frac{P_1 P_2}{P_3 P_3} V \right]^{2/3}$. It can be observed that the elastic displacements turn out to be first order homogeneous functions of applied normal forces. Under proportional loading, the elastic displacements of the body vary proportionately with corresponding applied forces. It is only under non-proportional variation of applied forces, that the body exhibits nonlinear mechanical behaviour.

Just like a flexible elastic sagging cable (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016), the deformed configuration of elastic liquid body is defined uniquely by its deformed dimensions $b_i = a_i + u_i$ where a_i denote the undeformed dimensions of the body subjected to the same forces. Thus, corresponding to each deformed equilibrium state b_i of the elastic liquid body, there exists a unique natural state a_i which can be reached by proportional unloading. This natural state coincides with the equilibrium state of the incompressible liquid body subjected to the same set of forces. This natural state also plays the role of instantaneous reference state relative to which the displacements of the elastic liquid body are defined. Liquid bodies lack unique passive natural reference state.

The tangent elastic flexibility matrix is obtained as $\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial P_j} = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+2}{3} \frac{u_i}{P_j}$ and one obtains the normalised rate-type relation $\dot{u}_i/u_i = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+2}{3} \dot{P}_j/P_j$. Three eigenvalues of the universal elastic liquid matrix in the above equation are obtained as (1, -1, -1). The distinct positive eigenvalue corresponds to the proportional force rate vector given by $(\dot{P}_1/P_1 = \dot{P}_2/P_2 = \dot{P}_3/P_3)$. In contrast, the two equal negative eigenvalues correspond to the orthogonal eigenvector represented by $(\dot{P}_1/P_1 + \dot{P}_2/P_2 + \dot{P}_3/P_3 = 0)$. It must be remembered that temporal variation

of forces introduces, apart from the variation in elastic displacements, the corresponding variation of side lengths, here called configurational displacements, as in the case of incompressible liquids.

The role of the elastic bulk modulus K is brought out by using the relation $u_i = \frac{pa_i}{3K}$, thus recasting the above matrix equation as below: $\dot{u}_i/a_i = \frac{(-3\delta_{ij}+2)p}{9K} \dot{P}_j/P_j$. Defining elastic strain rate as ($\dot{\varepsilon}_i = \dot{u}_i/a_i$) and using the identity ($D_{ie} = \dot{\varepsilon}_i$) for small elastic strains, one obtains the following rate-type constitutive matrix equation for purely elastic response: $D_{ie} = \frac{(-3\delta_{ij}+2)}{3K} \dot{\sigma}_j$. Eigenvalue analysis gives eigenvalues as $(\frac{1}{3K}, -\frac{1}{3K}, -\frac{1}{3K})$. The distinct positive eigenvalue corresponds to the isotropic stressing eigenvector ($\dot{\sigma}_1 = \dot{\sigma}_2 = \dot{\sigma}_3$) and dilatational mode ($D_{1e} = D_{2e} = D_{3e}$). In contrast, the two equal negative eigenvalues correspond to the deviatoric stressing eigenvector ($\dot{\sigma}_1 + \dot{\sigma}_2 + \dot{\sigma}_3 = 0$) and the equivoluminal mode ($D_{1e} + D_{2e} + D_{3e} = 0$).

The rate-type configurational and purely elastic constitutive equations for the liquid body can also be stated respectively as $\dot{a}_i = A_{ij}\dot{P}_j$ and $\dot{u}_i = B_{ij}\dot{P}_j$. Here, A_{ij} and B_{ij} represent the tangent configurational flexibility matrix and the tangent elastic flexibility matrix respectively. Incidentally, the tangent elastic flexibility matrix B_{ij} also plays the role of secant elastic flexibility matrix as in $u_i = B_{ij}P_j$. The total response $\dot{b}_i = \dot{a}_i + \dot{u}_i = \dot{v}_i$ of the elastic liquid body to general loading is obtained by superposing the configurational and elastic velocity vector components given respectively as \dot{a}_i and \dot{u}_i . Thus, total rate-type elasto-configurational constitutive equation is obtained as $\dot{b}_i = (A_{ij} + B_{ij})\dot{P}_j = C_{ij}\dot{P}_j$. The relevant expressions for the matrices A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and C_{ij} are given below:

$$A_{ij} = \frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3} \frac{a_i}{P_j} \quad B_{ij} = \frac{(-3\delta_{ij}+2)p}{9K} \frac{a_i}{P_j} \quad C_{ij} = \left[\frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3} + \frac{(-3\delta_{ij}+2)p}{9K} \right] \frac{a_i}{P_j}$$

The eigenvectors of the tangent configurational flexibility matrix A_{ij} and the tangent elastic flexibility matrix B_{ij} are identical. The eigenvectors of $C_{ij} = A_{ij} + B_{ij}$ are expected to be same and the eigenvalues of C_{ij} are obtained by algebraically adding the eigenvalues of the matrices A_{ij} and B_{ij} .

On dividing all the terms in the equation $\dot{b}_i = \dot{a}_i + \dot{u}_i$ by a_i , one obtains the following equation: $\frac{\dot{b}_i}{a_i} = \frac{\dot{a}_i}{a_i} + \frac{\dot{u}_i}{a_i}$. Defining the principal configurational and elastic rates of stretching as $D_{ic} = \frac{\dot{a}_i}{a_i}$ and $D_{ie} = \frac{\dot{u}_i}{a_i}$, the total principal rates of stretching $D_i = \frac{\dot{b}_i}{a_i}$ are obtained by adding the configurational and elastic rates of stretching as $D_i = D_{ic} + D_{ie}$. Further, knowing $\frac{\dot{P}_j}{P_j} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}_j}{p}$, the rate-type constitutive equations for the material point in principal coordinate system are stated as $D_i = \left[\frac{-3\delta_{ij}+1}{3} + \frac{(-3\delta_{ij}+2)p}{9K} \right] \frac{\dot{\sigma}_j}{p}$. Equivalently, $D_i = \left[-\frac{(3K+p)}{3Kp} \delta_{ij} + \frac{(3K+2p)}{9Kp} \right] \dot{\sigma}_j$.

Using the general relations as $\dot{\sigma}_i = \dot{\sigma}_m \delta_{ij} + \dot{s}_i$ and $D_i = \frac{D_{kk}}{3} \delta_{ij} + D'_i$, one gets the equation $\dot{\sigma}_m = B D_{kk}$ where $\dot{\sigma}_m$ represents the mean stress rate and the bulk modulus $B = K$. The deviatoric stress rate \dot{s}_i is related to the deviatoric rate of stretching D'_i as $D'_i = -(\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{3K}) \dot{s}_i$ or $\dot{s}_i = -(\frac{3Kp}{3K+p}) D'_i$.

The same arguments apply to the corresponding formulation in reference to the general coordinate system: Thus, one obtains the general relations as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \dot{\sigma}_m \delta_{ij} + \dot{s}_{ij}$ and $D_{ij} = \frac{D_{kk}}{3} \delta_{ij} + D'_{ij}$. In terms of bulk modulus $B = K$, The mean normal stress rate is related to rate of dilatation as $\dot{\sigma}_m = K D_{kk}$ and the deviatoric stress rate \dot{s}_{ij} is related to the deviatoric rate of stretching D'_{ij} as $D'_{ij} = -(\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{3K}) \dot{s}_{ij}$ or $\dot{s}_{ij} = -(\frac{3Kp}{3K+p}) D'_{ij}$. In view of this, the following converse version of rate-type constitutive equations for elastic liquids are established: $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = K D_{kk} \delta_{ij} - (\frac{3Kp}{3K+p}) D'_{ij}$ or $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = (\frac{K(3K+2p)}{3K+p}) D_{kk} \delta_{ij} - (\frac{3Kp}{3K+p}) D'_{ij}$. The above constitutive equation relating stress rate tensor components to the rate of stretching tensor components also resembles in form to the constitutive equation for isotropic linear elasticity using Lamé's constants λ and μ . In the present case, the following equivalences are established for Lamé-like coefficients: $\lambda \equiv \frac{K(3K+2p)}{3K+p}$ and $2\mu \equiv -\frac{3K}{3K+p}$. Indeed, the bulk modulus $B = \lambda + \frac{2}{3}\mu = K$. Thus, $\lambda + 2\mu \equiv K (\frac{3K-p}{3K+p})$ and $\mu \equiv -\frac{1}{2} (\frac{3Kp}{3K+p})$.

Using these expressions for stress rates and Cauchy-like dynamical equations of motion, the following Navier-like equations of motion for elastic liquids are derived:

$$K \left(\frac{3K+0.5p}{3K+p} \right) \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \left(\frac{1.5Kp}{3K+p} \right) \nabla^2 v_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$$

From the above equation, Navier-like equations of motion for incompressible liquids ($K = \infty$, $\frac{p}{K} = 0$, and $D_{kk} = 0$) is retrieved as $-\frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$.

Employing the arguments from the wave propagation in gases above, one obtains the following expressions for velocities of acoustic waves propagating as perturbations of the velocity field through elastic liquid media:

$$\text{Irrotational/longitudinal waves: } c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{K}{\rho} \left(\frac{3K-p}{3K+p} \right)} = \sqrt{\frac{K}{\rho} \left(\frac{3-p/K}{3+p/K} \right)}$$

$$\text{Equivoluminal/transverse waves: } c_2 = \sqrt{-\frac{p}{2\rho} \left(\frac{3K}{3K+p} \right)} = \sqrt{-\frac{p}{2\rho} \left(\frac{3}{3+p/K} \right)}$$

For the special limiting case of incompressible liquids ($K = \infty$), one obtains $c_1 = \infty$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{-p/2\rho}$. Thus, the incompressible liquids can support only transverse/equivoluminal waves with the same expression for finite speed as for gases. Further, in the absence of pressure or when the pressure happens to be quite low ($p \ll K$), one gets $c_1 = \sqrt{K/\rho}$ and $c_2 = 0$. This implies that the well-known Colladon-Strum (1837) expression for longitudinal/irrotational wave through water (Wirgin 2017) is obtained for the limiting case of vanishing pressure. As

the volumetric strain $\varepsilon_v = \frac{p}{K}$ is infinitesimally small, this expression seems to be approximately applicable for moderate pressure values as well.

To recapitulate, Hugoniot established that, not transversal, but only longitudinal waves can propagate through inviscid compressible fluids (Tokaty 1971). It seems that Hugoniot's conclusion is valid for compressible elastic liquids subjected to infinitely low-pressure fields. Even at moderate pressures, the effect of pressure on wave speeds is expected to be minimal as $\frac{p}{K}$ remains infinitesimally small.

5. Conclusions

In this part of the paper, the author's Sub-Elasticity Theory of nonlinear reversible materials and structures is presented for the first time. These sub-elastic systems are also shown to belong to the class of homogeneous mechanical systems. Thus, the theory of homogeneous functions constitutes the mathematical foundation of the physical theory of sub-elasticity. In place of unified theory of fluids, distinct sub-elastic theories of gases and liquids are constructed. Recognition of Cable-Liquid Analogy constituted the first step of the formulation of the theory. Rather than the material point, a rectangular parallelepipedon in equilibrium with applied normal compressive forces is chosen as the object of investigation. The main point of departure of the proposed theory is the derivation of rate-type constitutive equations for inviscid gases and liquids from their well-known equations of state. Only classical material constants like adiabatic index for gases and bulk modulus of elasticity for liquids are used in the derivations. Using these constitutive equations and Cauchy-like dynamical equations of motion, Navier-like kinetic equations of motion are derived for inviscid gases and liquids. The resulting neo-classical sub-elasticity theory replaces Euler's classical incomplete theory of inviscid fluids (1755).

Hyperbolic wave equations stated in terms of velocity field are deduced from Navier-like kinetic equations of motion. Like elastic waves through homogeneous isotropic linear elastic solids, both irrotational and equivoluminal equations are predicted to propagate through gases and liquids at different speeds. Laplace general thermodynamic expression for speed of arial sound (1816) is derived. A more general formula for speed of sound through elastic liquids is derived yielding Colladon - Sturm formula (1837) as a special case of vanishing pressure. Here, the continuity equation, Euler's equation of motion, Poisson's concepts of acoustic pressure and condensation, and the Laplace general formula for speed of sound are not invoked. Thus, a new sub-elastic wave theory of sound is proposed replacing Poisson's classical wave theory of sound (1820).

Correct derivation of the empirical formulae for the speed of propagation of irrotational sound waves partly confirms proposed theory. The most surprising, though unintended, contribution of the same theory is the prediction of the existence of transverse sound waves in both gases and liquids. The significance of the proposed neo-classical theory to the foundations of fluid mechanics, acoustics, and philosophy of science is critically examined in accompanying part of the paper (Benipal 2025).

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Acknowledgments:

To IIT Delhi where the Sub-Elasticity Theory was developed and SNIOE Delhi NCR where it was applied to fluid mechanics and acoustics.

To IIT Delhi where solid cutting-edge sponsored applied research contributions are celebrated but, equally importantly, slow-paced personal fundamental research is also tolerated.

To C. Truesdell for introducing rational mechanics, natural philosophy perspective, and the importance of historical context of fundamental research investigations.

Curriculum Vitae of the Author:

After retiring from IIT Delhi in 2021 after four-decade long service, Prof. Gurmail Singh Benipal served in Shiv Nadar Institution of Importance Delhi NCR till September 2024. His research interests include constitutive equations for concrete (damage-elasto-plasticity and thermo-chemo-viscoelasticity) and nonlinear structural theory (static, dynamic, and stability analysis of concrete structures, and sagging cable dynamics). He has supervised/co-supervised five doctoral students and published 29 journal papers and 30 conference papers. He has proposed new rational theories in these areas and written on schools of thought in engineering

sciences. From these theories of materials and structures identified as homogeneous mechanical systems, the author developed his unified theory of sub-elasticity. The present two-part paper is his first paper in fluid mechanics and acoustics.